

Figure S146. Regional gray matter volume differences between OCD and HC

Method	Contrast	Region	Side	BA	Voxels	X Y Z	t	Z	p _(FWE)
VBM	HC>OCD	n.s.							
	OCD>HC	n.s.							
SUIT	HC>OCD	n.s.							
	OCD>HC	n.s.							

Analysis of covariance thresholded at p<0.001 uncorrected and a minimum cluster-extent (ke) of 100, after which whole-brain cluster-corrected P(FWE)<0.05 are displayed. Coordinates (x/y/z) are in MNI standard space.

Abbreviations: BA, Brodmann area; L, left; R, right; M; midline; n.s., not significant

Figure S147. Effect of OCD severity on regional gray matter volume

Method	Contrast	Region	Side	BA	Voxels	X Y Z	t	Z	p _(FWE)
VBM	Severity+	n.s.							
	Severity-	medial OFC, rectus, ventral striatum	R	11	1098	8 27 -21	4.32	4.24	0.22
						10 40 -16	3.83	3.77	
						0 40 -16	3.22	3.19	
SUIT	Severity+	n.s.							
	Severity-	vermis lobules 4 and 5	M		156	2 -56 -15	3.99	3.93	0.004
						5 -49 -11	3.93	3.87	

Analysis of covariance thresholded at p<0.001 uncorrected and a minimum cluster-extent (ke) of 100, after which whole-brain cluster-corrected P(FWE)<0.05 are displayed. Coordinates (x/y/z) are in MNI standard space.

Abbreviations: BA, Brodmann area; L, left; R, right; M; midline; n.s., not significant; +, positive [1]; -, negative [-1] contrast

Figure S148. Effect of obsessive-compulsive symptom dimensionality on regional gray matter volume

Method	Contrast	Region	Side	BA	Voxels	X Y Z	t	Z	p _(FWE)
VBM	Cleaning and contamination+	n.s.							
	Cleaning and contamination-	n.s.							
	Harm and aggression+	n.s.							
	Harm and aggression-	n.s.							
	Sexual and religious+	n.s.							
	Sexual and religious-	n.s.							
	Symmetry and checking+	n.s.							
	Symmetry and checking-	n.s.							
	Hoarding+	n.s.							
Hoarding-	n.s.								
SUIT	Cleaning and contamination+	n.s.							
	Cleaning and contamination-	n.s.							
	Harm and aggression+	n.s.							
	Harm and aggression-	n.s.							
	Sexual and religious+	n.s.							
	Sexual and religious-	n.s.							
	Symmetry and checking+	n.s.							
	Symmetry and checking-	n.s.							
	Hoarding+	n.s.							
Hoarding-	n.s.								

Analysis of covariance thresholded at p<0.001 uncorrected and a minimum cluster-extent (ke) of 100, after which whole-brain cluster-corrected P(FWE)<0.05 are displayed. Coordinates (x/y/z) are in MNI standard space.

Abbreviations: BA, Brodmann area; L, left; R, right; M; midline; n.s., not significant; +, positive [1]; -, negative [-1] contrast

Figure S149. Regional gray matter volume differences between OCD with early versus late-onset

Method	Contrast	Region	Side	BA	Voxels	XYZ	t	Z	p _(FWE)
VBM	<i>Early onset>late onset</i>	n.s.							
	<i>Late onset>early onset</i>	n.s.							
SUIT	<i>Early onset>late onset</i>	n.s.							
	<i>Late onset>early onset</i>	n.s.							

Analysis of covariance thresholded at $p < 0.001$ uncorrected and a minimum cluster-extent (ke) of 100, after which whole-brain cluster-corrected $P(FWE) < 0.05$ are displayed. Coordinates (x/y/z) are in MNI standard space.

Abbreviations: BA, Brodmann area; L, left; R, right; M; midline; n.s., not significant

Figure S150. Effect of OCD duration on regional gray matter volume

Method	Contrast	Region	Side	BA	Voxels	XYZ	t	Z	p _(FWE)	
VBM	<i>Duration+</i>	superior and middle frontal gyri	R	8	1114	18 21 50	5.5	5.34	0.021	
						26 15 58	4.34	4.25		
			R	18	920	21 -70 -10	4.32	4.24	0.043	
	<i>Duration-</i>	n.s.					6 -93 -21	3.83	3.78	
							22 -84 -15	3.62	3.57	
SUIT	<i>Duration+</i>	lobule 8	L		341	-30 -57 -60	4.32	4.24	<0.001	
						-22 -65 -60	4.22	4.14		
						-22 -55 -59	3.92	3.86		
	<i>Duration-</i>	n.s.	lobule 8	R	1212	28 -67 -48	4.29	4.21	<0.001	
						28 -62 -60	3.95	3.89		
						22 -74 -54	3.69	3.64		

Analysis of covariance thresholded at $p < 0.001$ uncorrected and a minimum cluster-extent (ke) of 100, after which whole-brain cluster-corrected $P(FWE) < 0.05$ are displayed. Coordinates (x/y/z) are in MNI standard space.

Abbreviations: BA, Brodmann area; L, left; R, right; M; midline; n.s., not significant

Figure S151. Regional gray matter volume differences between OCD with and without mood and anxiety comorbidity

Method	Contrast	Region	Side	BA	Voxels	X Y Z	t	Z	p _(FWE)	
VBM	<i>Mood>non-mood</i>	n.s.								
	<i>Non-mood>mood</i>	n.s.								
	<i>Anxiety>non-anxiety</i>	n.s.								
	<i>Non-anxiety>anxiety</i>	n.s.								
SUIT	<i>Mood>non-mood</i>	crus 1-2, and lobule 8, and 7b	L		516	-37 -67 -37	4.56	4.46	<0.001	
						-20 -72 -40	4	3.93		
						-33 -59 -44	3.68	3.63		
			lobule 6	L		142	-33 -49 -23	4.36	4.28	0.006
			lobules 4 and 5 and the vermis	R	207	-29 -56 -20	3.32	3.28		
	5 -58 -9	4.12				4.05	0.001			
	14 -55 -12	3.98				3.92				
			vermis lobule 8	M		181	2 -70 -37	4.11	4.04	0.001
			lobule 8	L		134	-9 -65 -50	3.98	3.92	0.008
			lobule 8	L		106	-19 -58 -48	3.89	3.83	0.024
			vermis lobule 8	M		112	4 -61 -40	3.73	3.68	0.019
		<i>Non-mood>mood</i>	n.s.							
		<i>Anxiety>non-anxiety</i>	n.s.							
	<i>Non-anxiety>anxiety</i>	n.s.								

Analysis of covariance thresholded at p<0.001 uncorrected and a minimum cluster-extent (ke) of 100, after which whole-brain cluster-corrected P(FWE)<0.05 are displayed. Coordinates (x/y/z) are in MNI standard space.

Abbreviations: BA, Brodmann area; L, left; R, right; M; midline; n.s., not significant

Figure S152. Regional gray matter volume differences between OCD with and without past medication exposure

Method	Contrast	Region	Side	BA	Voxels	X Y Z	t	Z	p _(FWE)
VBM	<i>Med-naive>past SRI use</i>	n.s.							
	<i>Past SRI use>med-Naive</i>	n.s.							
SUIT	<i>Med-naive>past SRI use</i>	n.s.							
	<i>Past SRI use>med-Naive</i>	n.s.							

Analysis of covariance thresholded at p<0.001 uncorrected and a minimum cluster-extent (ke) of 100, after which whole-brain cluster-corrected P(FWE)<0.05 are displayed. Coordinates (x/y/z) are in MNI standard space.

Abbreviations: BA, Brodmann area; L, left; R, right; M; midline; n.s., not significant